

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Environmental costs of potato production in Cartagena: impact of sustainable agricultural practices

Potato production in the southern Mediterranean faces the challenge of balancing profitability and sustainability. The conventional production model, which relies heavily on chemical fertilizers, delivers high environmental and economic costs.

This study provides scientific evidence of the effectiveness of reducing inorganic fertilizers and the role of microorganisms (fungi and bacteria) in maintaining crop quality and yield. It also provides farmers with clear information to make informed decisions and improve the sustainability of their crops. At the same time, it provides policy makers with guidance on how to design incentives and regulations to promote more sustainable agricultural practices.

An environmental cost-benefit analysis (e-CBA) based on the monetization of impacts identified through life cycle analysis

(LCA) was conducted to compare four fertilization strategies in monetary terms: (1) traditional fertilization; (2) reduced fertilization; (3) reduced fertilization + nutrient-solubilizing fungi and bacteria; (4) reduced fertilization + nutrient-solubilizing bacteria.

Overall, environmental costs represent less than 13% of the farmer's gross margin (0.13 € per €).

The results suggest that optimizing fertilizer use and incorporating biological agents are the most important strategies to reduce environmental costs compared to conventional practices. The extent of the reduction depends on the combination used. The most effective strategy is reducing fertilizer use alone, leading to an 11% reduction in environmental costs compared to conventional practices.

1. Environmental costs (€ per € gross margin for the farmer) for each tested practice.

KEYWORDS

Potato cultivation, inorganic fertilizers, biological agents, impacts, environmental costs, e-CBA

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